

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

TERMS AND DIFFICULTIES IN TEACHING TERMINOLOGY

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Abstract

The article analyzes the problem of teaching terms and terminology to language learners. The article explains the difference between terms and ordinary words, the difficulties encountered when teaching terms to students, and the most optimal ways of teaching terms. At the same time, the evaluation process during classroom management and teaching of terms is also within the research scope of the article.

Keywords: terminology, terms, teaching ESP, assessment

Introduction. Terms are important part of English language. Every year new words, and terms include to the language. Terms are main keys of the academic material. Without knowing their meanings it is difficult to find the correct meaning. Technical dictionaries, glossaries, terminology lists, electronic term banks, and online dictionaries are created by documenting and organizing terms for specific purposes. Terms are formed in accordance with the rules for word formation in the standard form of the language. Terminology provides people with understanding how the components of specialized texts interact with the whole context, which is frequently an unconsciously used technique of knowledge acquisition. Terms are language components that communicate conceptual meaning within the confines of texts containing specialized knowledge. This process of meaning transmission is just as significant in understanding the nature of terms as the concept or concepts that it designates. Thus, linguistic analysis can be applied to terminological units.

Main part. *Difference between Word and Term.* The type of reference is the primary distinction between a term and a word. The term is described as being mono-referential in a highly precise idea relating to a certain area, field, or subject. It involves limits on language (lexical, syntactic, and semantic) and concepts (generic, portative, and casual). Terms consider the name of the supplied idea by starting with the concept (referent). Common words are frequently polysemous, and many of them have the same meanings, demonstrating the variety of language expression. Words with a single meaning and a sole referent, where the terms and the concept are specifically matched. Terminology is not only a more actively developing part of the vocabulary of any language, but also reflects progressive changes in society and science [3]. The term terminology is derived from the combination of the Latin terminus (term) and the Greek word logos - science. To understand the essence of the term, it is important to first refer to the word, which has a general meaning. A term, like a word, is itself a lexical category. It has a nominative character and expresses objects, events and certain concepts. Therefore, according to the general rule, it is not about the lexical meaning of the term, but about its function and content. As is known, terms form a special

layer in the lexical layer of the language and create a certain system as a special sign of scientific concepts.

The usage of terminology begins on very basic occasions in daily life and progresses to greater degrees of communication. Students are better able to understand the document's main point when they are familiar with the complex terminological details used in the technical and scientific contexts, and experts can communicate their ideas more effectively as a result. Learning terminology is the cornerstone of all academic disciplines. Without learning terminology, technicians and professionals are unlikely to understand the value of preserving a language for communication and cultural identity.

Difficulties in teaching English terms to the students. What makes a foreign language so difficult is the effort we have to make to transfer between linguistically complex structures. It's also challenging to learn how to think in another language. Above all, it takes time, hard work, and dedication. A limited range of terms are incorporated into common language, while popular words themselves serve as a continuing source of new terms. Language learners must study words from general technical, popular scientific, and specialized literature; it is advisable to incorporate broad terminological systems, terms, and their qualities into the process of teaching a foreign language. The word is typically clear, stylistically neutral, and systematic. One of the challenging issues in teaching English vocabulary to people with non-linguistic specialties is the study of terminological vocabulary, which has its own peculiarities. Its major objective is to help students assimilate the terminological vocabulary of this language subsystem, which enables them to actively employ words-terms when creating their own statements in a communicative manner in addition to accurately understanding the text [4]. Consequently, the capacity to comprehend and use language appropriately is understood to be a component of lexical abilities. It is necessary to present the main associations of terminological units, to present composite terminological combinations based on syntactic constructions, to familiarize students with the key functions of the term in these types of texts, in addition to carefully choosing textual, lexicographic, and other illustrative material. If an exercise program is devised, this objective is achievable.

The third stage's objective is to become proficient in the specialty's highly specialized words and formal speaking patterns. This stage's goals are the development of skills and abilities for using highly specialized terminological units in speech, familiarity with the sub-language's terminological system's structure, the development of skills and abilities to analyze a derived term's morphological structure, assimilation of the most effective word-formation models, familiarity with the particulars of a term's functioning, and definition of the main areas of terminology [1]. Teachers can recall the formal indications of a word by using strategies like crossword puzzles, constructing words from letters and syllables, making short words from longer ones, looking for a generalizing term in a chain of words, and inventing a new word by changing one letter in a given phrase. A range of gaming mechanics that are designed to improve the relationship between the word's visual and meaning. Finding a pair is the basis for the following games, such as word picture, word-translation, word-antonym, word-synonym, question-answer, and riddle-guess [5]. The development of skills and determination of word combinations, the structure of phrases, and the capacity to employ terminological terms are some of the most crucial requirements for the development and improvement of English speech among students. Students with non-linguistic backgrounds who can recognize and understand the grammatical and lexical components of English speech, establish logical relationships and connections between words, and comprehend the variety of words, forms, and constructions of the studied language can perceive English speech more successfully and freely. If students want to excel in the topic, they need assistance in learning the vocabulary and proper terminological phraseology for their level of ability. Teachers need to be aware that some words are difficult to define precisely in everyday language and are best comprehended in their technical form. However, a different strategy for clarifying terminology would be to provide pertinent instances that students are already familiar with. Thus, pupils will acquire new language units more successfully if they use terminological vocabulary. The teacher introduces academic language and technical terminology in phase 1, emphasizing the language's primary characteristics, such as abstractness, specificity, and completeness. In this stage, he or she also introduces the concepts of "corpus" and "terminological unit," which the pupils will require for the tasks that follow. The teacher might provide the lexicographic definitions of a few well-known terms or, as an alternative, allow the students to come up with some on their own. The significance of this first stage is that it helps the students recognize the distinctions between popular and scientific speech. Regardless of the differences in the pupils' backgrounds and objectives, the instructor must for this reason emphasize the value of terminology. To encourage increased involvement in the classroom and identify issues of shared interest among groups, the instructor must critically build on the knowledge of the students. Additionally, he or she must give the students access to internet databases of scholarly articles that will serve as the foundation for the

subsequent exploratory activity. The second way of teaching is one in which students gradually learn to detect and extrapolate from lexical patterns in terms without explicit instruction; in other words, terminology is learnt by inference. It is also expected that the prefixes, roots, and suffixes of the various terms appear frequently enough and in appropriate contexts to allow learners to accurately infer meaning.

The more specialized L2 vocabulary must be learned separately from the more general L2 vocabulary. When learning a new word, whether technical or not, the student must understand its definition and usage. Many low-level words, for example, allow learners to map the word's form onto an existing meaning in their native language. In other situations, the learner must also learn the new meaning. When it comes to acquiring terminology that is specialized to a subject, this is typically the case. Students studying terms in a field they are unfamiliar with not only have to acquire a new form, but frequently also a new notion. We must understand how students acquire subject-specific vocabulary in L2. Examining the students' reading notes is one approach to do this because they reveal information about how they comprehend the material and the methods they use to learn the new vocabulary [4]. Students frequently take notes as they read to learn, and numerous studies have shown that doing so can predict test achievement. Since taking notes includes numerous processes, including comprehension, selection, and production, it encourages thorough understanding. Students must first comprehend a text in order to take effective notes, and then they must be able to choose material that is pertinent to their learning objective. They must next convert that pertinent data into a manner that will make the reading material simple to obtain and understand for them. Thus, notes can offer useful information on how students approach learning and what portion of the body of knowledge they are familiar with.

Learner assessment The processes and techniques used to evaluate a learner's proficiency in the target language are referred to as assessment. To achieve the desired outcomes, both formative and summative forms of assessment should be used. According to Douglas (2000), a specific purpose language test is one in which the tasks and content are authentically representative of the target situation and the test content and methods are derived from an analysis of the features of a specific target language use situation [5]. Assessment is based on need analysis and is dependent on the course objectives.

Managing Classes. Teacher must first establish learning objectives before incorporating them into an instructional program with appropriate activity timing. One of the key responsibilities will be choosing, arranging, and designing the course materials. Teacher will also be assisting the students in their efforts and giving them feedback on their progress.

Setting Objectives and Goals. Teachers set up the learning environment in the classroom and establish both long-term and short-term goals for student success. The key to creating a syllabus with achievable objectives that takes into account the students' concerns in

the learning environment is your understanding of their potential.

So, teaching and learning terms in English language for learners is difficult process. It requires specific methodology and techniques for teachers. Teachers for teaching English for specific purposes must skillful to gain high results in their learning process. But it is very important for teachers to get teachers special training in the analysis and material choice which enable them to meet the specific needs and high expectations for their learners. So, teachers must be selective in teaching terms to the English language learning classroom. In order to give English foreign language students access to more in-depth academic learning, emphasis should be made on improving their language skills when teaching academic reading. The learning process will be successful if the methods of teaching

terms, purpose, teaching strategies, evaluation process are set up correctly.

References

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